

APPENDIX – Script of the semi structured interview

Part 1 – Practice Script

Personal Data

Name:

E-mail:

Age:

Gender:

Male

Female

City/State:

Scholarship:

Graduation

Specialization

Master

Doctor

Others: _____

Formation Area:

Administration

Computing/Informatics

Communication

Others: _____

Role:

Director

Project manager

Technical Leader

Others: _____

Professional experience time

1. How many years of experience do you have in the Information Technology (IT) Area?
2. How many years of experience do you have in Project management/technical leadership/software Development?
3. How many years of experience do you have in projects with distributed teams?

About the organization

4. What is the name of the organization where you work?
5. What is the size of your organization?
 - Micro – up to 9 employees
 - Small - from 10 to 49 employees

- Medium – from 50 to 99 employees
 - Large –more than 100 employees
6. Your organization has subsidiaries or branches in other places?
- Yes
 - No
- Where _____
7. The subsidiaries or branches have a specific role in the development of global projects? How every branch participates in the DSD projects?
8. Your organization is certified in any quality model (CMMI, Mps.Br, ISO e etc.)?
- Yes
 - No
- What _____
- When the certification occurred? _____
9. What was the criterion or motivation to the adoption of projects with geographically distributed teams?

Characteristics of the DSD Project

10. Project type:
- Innovation
 - Maintenance
 - Development of a new product
 - Others _____
11. What is the dispersion level of the Project that you work?
- National
 - Continental
 - Global
12. How many organizations are involved in this Project? Outsourced or subsidiary company?
- 1 organization
 - 2 organizations
 - 3 organizations OR
 - 1 subsidiary
 - 2 subsidiaries
 - 3 subsidiaries
 - Other _____
13. How many distributed software Development teams exist in the current DSD Project?
- 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
- Specify the quantity _____
14. How many people exist in every DSD team?
15. What are the places (cities, states or countries) where are found every team?
16. The policies and Development standards of the software Development in the organization are followed by all the geographically distributed teams?
- Are totally followed

- Are partially followed
- Every team have their own standards
- There are not defined standards

17. In the DSD Project you participates is (are) adopted any software development methodologie(s) (eg.: Rup, Agile methodologies, etc.)

Communication in DSD

18. In your opinion, what is the impact of the DSD over the way the teams communicate with each other?
19. In what moment the communication planning is done for the DSD projects?
20. There exist meetings for integration of the teams in the initial stages of the DSD projects? What is the impact of this action in the project?
21. There is somebody responsible by the communication of the DSD Project?
22. What are the attributions (responsibilities) of the responsible by the communication in relation to the distributed (remote) teams?
23. When and how the distributed teams communicate with each other?
24. In what moment of the Project the team members have a greater need to meet in person?
25. How long the teams work together? (Familiarity)?
26. Throughout the Project, how many times on average the geographically distributed teams physically gather?
27. What make the teams to have the need to communicate in the Project? What are the purposes? How often?
28. What is the Software Development stage in the DSD context that demands more communication dedication? Why? (Requirement, Analysis, Development, Test or Deployment)?
29. What are the main communication difficulties (problems) in the DSD context, and how you manage/solve them in your project?
30. What were the problems most difficult to solve about communication during the execution of the project?
31. In what priority order these problems must be solved or managed?
32. Do you remember of well succeeded communication practices in your DSD Project? What were they? Why do you believe that they resulted in success?
33. In your opinion, how the communication would be improved or evolved?
34. The distributed teams communicate mostly in a synchronous or asynchronous way? Generally what are the used tools?
35. The members of the geographically distributed teams know who to call when having communication related problems?
36. In your opinion, is relevant for DSD projects to have a maturity model to measure the quality of the communication?
- Yes
 - No
 - Maybe
- Justify: _____
37. Would you like to add some information that you think is relevant for the study?